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FEATURES OF THE SOUTH KOREAN EDUCATION SYSTEM AND POSSIBILITIES OF THEIR APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes South Korea's education policy. It examines the unique features and trends in the development of education in South Korea, analyzes the current state and compares it with the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It also provides suggestions based on the practice of South Korea.

Key words: South Korea, policy, features, stages of education, science, Korean education system, modern methodology.

INTRODUCTION

South Korea holds one of the highest positions in the world in terms of quality and systematicity of education. Korean students continuously acquire new knowledge and study throughout the day. Respect for science and a firm belief in the necessity of constant self-improvement play an important role in the learning process.

South Korea is one of the world's leading economic powers. Within a few decades, this country has transformed from a developing nation into an industrialized country exporting high-tech products. This development is largely attributed to the improvement of the country's education system. According to many scholars, the country's economic success is the result of an effective education system that prepares highly qualified workforce necessary for economic growth.

The South Korean government pays special attention to the country's education system, which is also viewed as an effective means of strengthening national power. Reforming school education is one of the most important tasks facing the country's government, as the level of the education system should correspond to the country's level of economic development. Issues of school education reform in South Korea have gained particular significance. The general education school is one of the main components of the entire education system undergoing active reforms. School serves as the primary means of shaping an individual's personality and largely determines the student's future career choice [1].

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Foreign scholars such as I.A. Tolstokulakov [2], A.N. Lankov [3], G.V. Mikaberidze [4], S. Park [5], E.Kh. Li [6], and B.G. Chung [7] have studied issues related to the main directions of modernizing the education system and organizations in South Korea. Among Uzbek scholars, D. Miralieva [8], N. Fayzullaeva [9], M. Jo'raev [10], and others have also examined these issues.

Regarding the level of study of South Korea's general education school system, it should be noted that foreign researchers such as R. Jones [11] and D. Mani [12] have also explored this topic. These research works cover only certain aspects of the South Korean education system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the article is to study and analyze the distinctive features of the South Korean education system and the possibilities of their application in Uzbekistan. The research utilized methods of observation, data comparison and analysis, scientific abstraction, and data grouping, based on which conclusions were drawn.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In our research, it is necessary to highlight two specific aspects of Korean education at the current stage: the policy of equality principle and special emphasis on education and upbringing.

First, the education system developed on the basis of the declared principle of equality. The government's task is to ensure equal opportunities for everyone, regardless of gender, religion, geographical location, and socio-economic status.

Secondly, Korean society traditionally places high value on education and upbringing. The demand for quality education remains high, and as a result, intense competition for admission to higher education institutions and high expenditures on private tutoring have become some of the main consequences.

Currently, the education system in South Korea is considered one of the most developed and effective systems in the world.

Pre-school education in South Korea

In South Korea, preschool education plays an important role in preparing children for school and developing their social and personal skills.

Pre-school education in Korea covers children aged 3 to 6 years. The main forms of preschool education are traditional kindergartens, early development centers, and private institutions. Public and private kindergartens offer various programs aimed at the comprehensive development of children.

The goal of preschool education is not only to prepare for primary school studies but also to contribute to personal development, the formation of social skills, and the achievement of emotional maturity. Emphasis is placed on games and active teaching methods, which allow children to develop creativity and critical thinking. Pre-school education programs are diverse and include many approaches. They may include classes in mathematics, languages, art, and physical education. Teachers actively use play-based learning methods, making the process engaging and enjoyable.

Pre-school education in the country is fee-based. Its cost varies depending on the type of institution, location, and offered programs. Public kindergartens are usually less expensive, and in some cases, subsidies are provided by the state. The average cost can range from 200,000 to 400,000 Korean won per month (approximately \$130-280 USD).

Private kindergartens are generally more expensive and, depending on the prestige and quality of education, can cost from 400,000 to 800,000 Korean won (\$280-560) or more per month. South Korea has a system of preschool education subsidies, which allows some families to receive financial assistance to cover kindergarten expenses. Low-income families may be eligible for additional allowances and assistance in paying for kindergarten [13].

School education in South Korea

In South Korea, the school education system is divided into three stages.

Primary school. Children begin their studies at the age of 6. Primary school lasts for 6 years and provides basic knowledge in core subjects such as Korean language, mathematics, natural sciences, and art.

Middle school. After completing primary school, children enter a three-year middle school. This stage involves a deeper study of subjects and the development of critical thinking.

High school. Completing school education involves spending 3 years in high school. Here, students can choose between academic and vocational tracks. In higher grades, special attention is paid to preparing for university entrance exams (Table 1).

1-table. South Korea's school system [14].

Stage	Grade	Notes
Primary School (6 years)	1-6	Compulsory education (free, 9 years)
Middle School (3 years)	1-3	
High School (3 years)	1-3	Compulsory education (paid, 3 years)

Education in South Korea is considered one of the best education systems in the world. South Korea holds one of the leading positions in international education quality rankings. High achievements in mathematics and sciences make Korean students competitive on a global scale.

Particular attention is paid to exam preparation, especially for the CSAT (College Scholastic Ability Test), which plays a decisive role in university admissions.

School education, particularly primary and secondary education, is mainly free for citizens of the country. However, there are some aspects related to paid education. Primary and secondary education in public schools is provided free of charge. Nevertheless, parents have to bear the costs of additional services such as learning materials, school uniforms, and meals (Table 2).

2-table. Organization of the educational process in a general education school in South Korea [14].

School level	Total lessons per year	Lesson duration	Total annual lesson time	Study period
Primary	5892	40 minutes	235 680 minutes	6 years
Middle	3366	45 minutes	151 470 minutes	3 years
High	3468	50 minutes	173 400 minutes	3 years

The duration of study is clearly defined for each grade level, but if a student demonstrates high knowledge and skills, a decision may be made to promote them to the next grade more quickly. This process is carried out through a decision by a special commission, which assesses the student's knowledge and recognizes the completion of a certain grade level.

Private schools require tuition fees. The cost of education can vary significantly depending on the school's reputation and curriculum. Private schools often offer specialized programs, which attracts many parents.

Additionally, many students attend "Hagwon" (private educational institutions) that offer supplementary courses in various subjects. These classes are usually paid and can significantly increase the overall cost of education.

Higher education in South Korea

The South Korean higher education system encompasses universities and colleges. Educational institutions offer a variety of programs ranging from undergraduate to graduate and doctoral studies.

Universities are the primary institutions providing education in numerous fields such as science, engineering, arts, and humanities. Undergraduate programs at universities typically last 4 years, while graduate programs last 2 years.

Colleges, on the other hand, are educational institutions focused on practical education and training specialists in specific fields, such as business, technology, and the arts. College programs typically last 2-3 years.

Higher education in South Korea is predominantly fee-based. Tuition fees at public universities are generally lower than at private universities. The average tuition fee for public universities can range from 3 million to 7 million Korean Won (approximately \$20,000-50,000 USD) per year, depending on the program and specialty.

Tuition fees at private universities are typically higher, ranging from 6 million to 10 million won per year (approximately US\$40,000-70,000). These institutions often offer specialized programs and modern facilities. In addition to tuition fees, students must also consider the costs of educational materials, accommodation, and daily expenses. For instance, accommodation costs may vary depending on whether the student chooses university dormitories or private housing [13].

Many universities offer scholarships for international students. These scholarships can be awarded based on academic achievements, financial need, or other criteria. Although higher education is not entirely free, there are various mechanisms and programs that enable Korean students to reduce their educational expenses.

Many universities offer scholarships to students based on academic achievements, as well as to children from low-income families. Some government programs also provide financial support for students. Virtually all universities in South Korea have campuses with dormitories, dining facilities, gyms, and libraries.

There are various social initiatives and aid programs for students in the country aimed at both reducing tuition fees and covering other expenses such as accommodation and meals. Local authorities and various organizations may also offer grants and financial support for specific categories of students.

The South Korean education system is distinguished by its systematic approach, modern teaching methods, and advanced technologies. In adapting it to the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is essential to thoroughly analyze the educational policies, socio-economic conditions, and cultural characteristics of both countries.

First and foremost, South Korea's experience in placing special emphasis on STEM disciplines should be implemented in Uzbekistan. In Korean schools, subjects such as mathematics, physics, computer science, biology, and chemistry are at the core of the educational process. The role of these subjects in the curriculum is aimed not only at developing theoretical knowledge but also at fostering practical skills and competencies. When implementing STEM in Uzbekistan, it is essential to enrich the educational process with more engaging and interactive methods. To achieve this, it is crucial to establish modern laboratories and utilize innovative technologies to provide students with knowledge that can be applied in practice.

Secondly, the widespread use of digital technologies in the educational process in South Korea is one of the main factors contributing to its success. Digital platforms that provide a personalized approach to each student serve to enhance learning effectiveness.

These platforms help tailor the learning process to the individual pace and level of student learning. In Uzbekistan, it is necessary to create digital educational platforms and implement them across all schools and higher education institutions. It is also possible to expand opportunities for the development of distance learning by adopting the experience of South Korea. This is particularly important in addressing issues related to the quality of education in rural areas.

Thirdly, South Korea's approach to training highly qualified specialists in the higher education system is significant for Uzbekistan. South Korean universities are distinguished by their close cooperation with employers and their efforts to link research work with practical applications. It is recommended that Uzbek universities study the experience of implementing dual degree programs, organizing internships, and participating in international scientific projects in collaboration with South Korean universities.

Fourthly, drawing on South Korea's experience, it is necessary to introduce new methods for developing students' practical skills in Uzbekistan's schools. For example, project-based learning can be widely implemented in schools. This method allows students to acquire theoretical knowledge through practical research and projects. This approach not only increases students' interest but also cultivates their ability to think independently and solve problems.

Fifthly, one of the most important features of the South Korean education system is its focus on sustainability and environmental education within the learning process. To strengthen environmental awareness in Uzbek schools and instill a culture of nature preservation in the younger generation, it is beneficial to study and apply South Korean sustainable development programs.

In conclusion, the modern South Korean education system opens up numerous opportunities for Uzbekistan. By adapting South Korean experiences in areas such as introducing innovations into the educational process, fostering students' creative and independent thinking, and enhancing teachers' qualifications, it is possible to elevate our national education system to a new level.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the South Korean education system presents significant opportunities for Uzbekistan to implement innovative approaches. Utilizing this country's experience in areas such as introducing modern technologies, enhancing teacher qualifications, developing STEM programs, widely implementing collaborative work, and strengthening environmental education will elevate the national education system to a new level. In this process, it is crucial to consider national characteristics and develop approaches tailored to local conditions.

The South Korean education system is recognized as one of the most advanced in the world, with its key features being high efficiency, technological innovations, and systematic organization of the educational process. Drawing from Korea's experience, it is possible to develop a series of strategic proposals for the advancement of Uzbekistan's education system.

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